

Figure S1. Treatment course of the twins.

The line graphs show the levels of Ca, P, and PTH. The x-axis indicates the month from the first visit. Alfacalcidol and calcium lactate was administrated to increase the Ca levels.

Figure S2. Methylation analysis of the *GNAS* locus by methylation-specific restriction enzyme qPCR.

Methylated ratios were calculated based on the Ct values of HpaII-digested samples. The error bars represent the standard deviation.

Figure S3. SNP array analysis of family members.

Plots of log R ratio and B allele frequency in chromosome 20 of family members.

Table S1. Candidate factors

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AICDA, APOBEC1, ARID4A, ARID4B, CTCF, DNMT1, DNMT3A, DNMT3B, DNMT3L, DPPA3, Histone H1, KDM1A, KDM1B, KHDC3L, MBD3, MTA2, NLRP2, NLRP5, NLRP7, OOE, PADI6, POU5F1, SMCHD1, SOX2, TET1, TET2, TRIM28, UHRF1, YY1, ZAR1, ZBTB33, ZFP42, ZFP57
